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KONTROLA KVALITETA DIJETETSKIH SUPLEMENATA NA BAZI RESVERATROLA**Veljko Ćučuz^{1,2}, Svetlana Stojkov³, Jelena Cvejić Hogervorst², Ljilja Torović²**¹**Beni apoteka, Kosovska ⁴, Beograd, Srbija**²**Univerzitet u Novom Sadu, Medicinski fakultet, Katedra za farmaciju, Novi Sad, Srbija**³**Univerzitet Privredna akademija, Farmaceutski fakultet, Novi Sad, Srbija**

Kriterijumi koji dijetetski suplementi (DS) treba da zadovolje u pogledu kvaliteta nijesu precizno definisani. DS se u prometu najčešće nalaze u obliku kapsula i tableta, stoga je poželjno provjeriti kvalitet doznih oblika u pogledu ujednačenosti mase i sadržaja, i brzine rastvorljivosti aktivne supstance prema dostupnim farmakopejskim zahtjevima za lijekove. Cilj rada je ispitivanje kvaliteta DS na bazi resveratrola koje može ukazati na potencijalne nedostatke ostalih suplemenata u prometu.

Sedam DS na bazi resveratrola ispitano je prema zahtjevima European Pharmacopoeia (Ph. Eur.) 6 za lijekove u pogledu ujednačenosti mase i sadržaja doznih jedinica i brzine oslobađanja aktivnih komponenti. Za određivanje ujednačenosti mase doznih jedinica korišćena je analitička vaga. HPLC metodom je određivana ujednačenost sadržaja resveratrola, dok je ispitivanjem rastvorljivosti koncentracija oslobođenog resveratrola u acetatnom puferu pH 4,5 nakon 45 minuta rastvaranja kvantifikovana HPLC metodom.

Pet od sedam ispitanih suplemenata bilo je u skladu sa zahtjevima Ph. Eur. 6 za lijekove u pogledu ispitivanja uniformnosti mase i uniformnosti sadržaja doznih jedinica. Testiranjem rastvorljivosti vizuelnom procenom konstatovano je da kod doznih jedinica tri DS nije bilo čvrstih ostataka u kadicama aparata. Djelimično se rastvorio jedan suplement, dok su tri ostala skoro nerastvorena. Resveratrol je kvantifikovan kod samo tri suplementa, dok ostali suplementi nisu oslobodili detektabilnu količinu resveratrola. Ni jedan suplement nije ispunio zahtjeve Ph. Eur. 6 za lijekove gdje se nakon 45 minuta mora osloboditi minimum 75% od deklarisanog sadržaja resveratrola.

Dozne jedinice skoro polovine ispitanih uzoraka nijesu se raspale u potpunosti tokom testa disolucije, odnosno nijedan suplement nije oslobodio značajnu količinu resveratrola, što upućuje na potrebu poboljšanja rastvorljivosti resveratrola iz ovih preparata kao što je inkorporiranje resveratrola u liposome.

Ključne riječi: Dijetetski suplementi, resveratrol, kontrola kvaliteta

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QUALITY CONTROL OF RESVERATROL-BASED DIETARY SUPPLEMENTS**Veljko Ćučuz^{1,2}, Svetlana Stojkov³, Jelena Cvejić Hogervorst², Ljilja Torović²***¹Benu Pharmacy, Kosovska ⁴, Belgrade, Serbia**²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Novi Sad, Serbia**³University Business Academy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Novi Sad, Serbia*

Quality criteria for dietary supplements (DS) are not precisely defined. DS are most often found as capsules or tablets on the market, and therefore it is desirable to check the quality of dosage forms in terms of uniformity of mass and content, and dissolution time of the active substance according to available Pharmacopoeia requirements for drugs. The aim of this study is to test the quality of resveratrol-based DS which can indicate potential disadvantages of other supplements on the market.

Seven resveratrol-based DS were tested according to requirements by European Pharmacopoeia 6 for drugs regarding uniformity of mass and content of dosage units and release time of active components. Analytical balance was used for determining uniformity of mass of dosage units. HPLC method was used to determine uniformity of resveratrol content, while the concentration of resveratrol in acetate buffer pH 4.5 after 45 minutes of dissolution was quantified by HPLC method.

Five out of seven supplements were in line with European Pharmacopoeia 6 requirements for drugs regarding uniformity of mass and content of dosage units. Visual assessment of dissolution test determined that there were no solid residues in dispensers for dosage units of three dietary supplements. One supplement has partially dissolved while three remained almost undiluted. Resveratrol was quantified in three supplements while other supplements haven't released detectable amount of resveratrol. None of the supplements has met requirements of European Pharmacopoeia 6 for drugs where a minimum of 75% of declared resveratrol content must be released after 45 minutes.

Dosage units of almost half of the tested samples haven't entirely dissolved during the dissolution test, that is, no supplement has released a significant amount of resveratrol, which indicates the need for improving the resveratrol dissolution in these preparations such as incorporating resveratrol in liposomes.

Keywords: Dietary supplements, resveratrol, quality control